

A Review

Periodontal Microsurgery: Achieving Unprecedented Precision

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Abstract

The use of magnification in medical and dental procedures, particularly in endodontics, has been long acknowledged. However, its application in periodontics is not as widely recognized. This article aims to highlight the application of microsurgical principles in various periodontal surgical procedures and advocate for the integration of microscopes into periodontal practice. A review of recent periodontal journals was conducted, along with a search of databases such as PubMed, Medline, and Google Scholar for relevant literature published up to 2017. The Medical Subject Headings (MeSH) terms used included "periodontal microsurgery" and "minimally invasive periodontal surgery." The available literature specific to periodontal surgical procedures was analyzed and summarized. The analysis reveals that using magnification in periodontal practice improves visual acuity, offers ergonomic benefits, reduces patient morbidity, accelerates healing, and enhances patient acceptance.

Introduction

Over the past few decades, dental sciences have undergone significant changes in both concepts and techniques. While the use of loupes and surgical operating microscopes for magnification in various medical and surgical procedures is widely recognized, their adoption in dentistry, particularly periodontics, needs broader attention. This article reviews the applications of periodontal microsurgery, covering procedures from mucogingival surgeries to regenerative techniques and implant dentistry. Additionally, it provides a brief overview of microsurgical principles, ergonomics, and instruments.

History

Daniel broadly defined microsurgery as surgery performed under microscopic magnification.¹ Serafin described microsurgery as a methodology that involves

modifying and refining existing surgical techniques using magnification to enhance visualization, applicable across all specialties.²

Apotheker and Jako introduced the commercial operating microscope to dentistry in 1981.³ Microsurgery was introduced to periodontics in 1992.⁴ In 1993, Shanellec and Tibbetts conducted a continuing education course on periodontal microsurgery at the annual meeting of the American Academy of Periodontology.⁵

Microsurgical Triad

The operating microscope offers three distinct benefits: illumination, magnification, and increased precision in surgical skill delivery,

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collectively known as the microsurgical triad. (figure 1)⁶ Illumination, achieved through fiberoptic technology, has enhanced the ability to focus light on specific areas and is a standard feature of surgical operating microscopes. Magnification, the second component, can be provided by loupes or the operating microscope, each with its own advantages and limitations.⁷ Loupes can be simple, compound, or prism in design, available as eyeglasses or attached to a headset.⁸ Compound and prism designs offer superior magnification and are commonly used in dentistry.⁹

Caplan's review article offers an excellent comparison of different types of loupes. In a well-established periodontal microsurgical practice, 70%-80% of procedures can be performed at a magnification of $\times 10$ – $\times 20$ with a surgical operating microscope. The remaining procedures can be conducted with loupes at $\times 6$ – $\times 8$ magnification, utilizing enhanced motor skills developed during training with the surgical microscope.¹⁰ At a magnification of $\times 20$, hand movement precision approaches 10 μm , and visual resolution approaches 1 μm , making proprioceptive guidance less valuable under the microscope.¹¹ Increased precision in surgical skill delivery, the third component of the microsurgical triad, results synergistically from enhanced illumination and magnification.¹²

Ergonomics in Microsurgery

For effective microsurgery, the operating

surgeon must maintain a relaxed state of mind, good body comfort and posture, a well-supported hand, and a stable instrument-holding position.⁷ To achieve precise and controlled finger movements, the ulnar surface of the forearm and wrist should rest on a flat surface, angled in a dorsiflexion position at approximately 20° to minimize muscle tremor from both unintentional and intentional actions.^{13,14}

The surgeon should sit upright with a straight back, head erect, and both feet flat on the floor, ensuring the thighs are parallel to the floor. Movements should be efficient, producing purposeful and deliberate motions.

The pen grip, or internal precision grip, (figure 2) is the most commonly recommended grip for microsurgical procedures. It offers greater stability than other hand grips due to the tripod formed by the fingers, with the middle finger supporting the instrument.^{13,15} Beginners should start with the pen grip to master basic manipulations before attempting more freehand positions.⁷

Ergonomic benefits, including reduced shoulder, neck, and back problems, improved vision, and less eye fatigue, have been reported in qualitative research from Vancouver Community College in British Columbia.^{16,17} These ergonomic advantages may significantly influence the widespread adoption of magnification in the dental profession.

Microsurgical Instruments

Smaller instruments can be used with greater precision due to improved visual acuity. For proper handling and high-precision movement, microsurgical instruments should be slightly top-

heavy, circular in cross-section, and approximately 18 cm in length.¹⁸ Shorter instruments with a rectangular cross-sectional design are not ideal for precise manipulation in microsurgery. These instruments typically have a color-coated surface to prevent an unfavorable metallic glare from the microscope light.⁷ To avoid hand and arm fatigue, the weight of microsurgical instruments should not exceed 15–20 grams.¹⁸ Needle holders should have a locking force that does not exceed 50 grams (0.5 N), (figure 3) as low locking forces reduce precision and high locking forces can cause tremors.

Figure 3- Relative size of microsurgical and conventional needle holder

Manufacturers offer sets of periodontal microsurgical instruments made of steel or titanium. Titanium instruments are stronger, lighter, non-magnetic, and more expensive than stainless steel, but they can distort easily if not handled properly. During sterilization and transportation, care must be taken to prevent the tips of the instruments from touching each other.¹⁸

A basic set of microsurgical instruments includes a microscalpel holder, needle holder, microscissors, microforceps, and elevators. (figure 4) Blades used in ophthalmic surgery can also be utilized for periodontal microsurgery due to their small size and extreme sharpness, allowing for clean, non-ragged incisions that promote primary intention wound healing. Needle holders, elevators, and mirrors are downsized from those used in conventional periodontal surgery. Small tissue pieces can be removed more efficiently with micro-Vannas scissors.¹⁹ To prevent slippage while tying knots, forceps with flat-surfaced tips or needle holders with a finely coated diamond grain surface are recommended.²⁰

To minimize tissue trauma, the sharpest needles are preferred, such as spatula needles (6.6 mm long with a 140° curvature) with microtips or reverse cutting needles with precision tips.^{20,21} For

Figure 4- Periodontal microsurgical knives

microsurgical periodontal procedures, 3/8" circular needles are usually effective. Needle lengths of 13–15 mm are suitable for papillary sutures in posterior areas, 10–12 mm for the anterior region, and 5–8 mm for approximating vertical incisions.¹⁸ Most periodontal microsurgical suturing is performed with sutures ranging from 6-0 to 9-0 in size. (figure 5) Monofilament nonabsorbable sutures are preferable and should be removed at the earliest biologically acceptable time.²² Suture materials like Vicryl® Plus, coated with triclosan, are emerging alternatives to minimize microbial passage along the sutures.^{23,24} The combined use of small needles and sutures under magnification allows for wound closure with sufficient tension and minimal dead space.

Microsurgical Suturing

Suturing techniques in microsurgery differ significantly from those in conventional surgery. In microsurgical procedures, the needle should penetrate the tissues perpendicularly and exit at equal distances on both sides. The suture bite size should be approximately 1.5 times the tissue thickness to ensure proper wound approximation.²⁵

Knot tying under the microscope is performed using instrument ties, with a microsurgical needle holder in the dominant hand and a microsurgical tissue pickup in the non-dominant hand.⁷ The integrity of a knot is best maintained with square

knots, and the preferred knot combination is a surgeon's knot followed by a square knot. Adding extra ties to a knot increases its bulk without enhancing its strength or integrity.¹⁹

Recently, a novel suturing technique combining vertical and horizontal mattress sutures supported at temporarily splinted interdental contact points has been described. This method ensures proper soft-tissue alignment and atraumatic displacement in minimally invasive periodontal plastic procedures and in the management of soft tissues around implants.²⁶

Figure 5- Relative size of different sutures

Clinical Applications

Periodontal microsurgery is an evolution of conventional periodontal surgery, aiming to reduce surgical trauma and enhance patient care.

Root Surface Debridement: The importance of root debridement is universally recognized as a crucial component of periodontal therapy.^{27,28,29,30} Thorough root surface debridement is more critical for the improved outcome of periodontal treatment than the choice of grafting modality.^{31,32} Studies have shown that root instrumentation is more effective when performed under illumination, resulting in better early healing and less postoperative pain.^{33,34} Microultrasonic instruments, which are smaller (about 0.2–0.6 mm in diameter) and have variable power settings (25,000 to over 40,000 cycles per second), allow for subgingival treatment in deep pockets with minimal risk of overinstrumentation. These instruments have active working sides on all surfaces and can deliver ultrasonically activated lavage in the working area with minimal water spray.³⁵ Magnification improves root surface debridement by enhancing the clinician's ability to differentiate calculus from tooth surface and biofilm at a microscopic level, revealing morphological contours of both

supragingival and subgingival tooth surfaces and accurately reproducing working end angles during instrumentation.³⁶

Periodontal Regeneration: Over the past decades, modifications in surgical procedures and their clinical effectiveness for periodontal regeneration of intrabony defects have been extensively studied.^{37,38,39,40,41} Many authors have proposed the use of a microsurgical approach for treating isolated or multiple intrabony defects.^{42,43,44,45,46,47,48,49,50} The microsurgical approach in regenerative therapy offers improved illumination and magnification of the surgical field, allowing for proper access and debridement of the intrabony defect with increased accuracy and minimal trauma.^{51,52} Additionally, the ability to achieve and maintain primary wound closure minimizes bacterial contamination, providing more favorable conditions for periodontal regeneration.⁵³ This approach also results in minimal marginal tissue recession, improved esthetics, limited intra- and postoperative morbidity, and high patient acceptance and satisfaction.^{54,55} However, the probing depth reduction and clinical attachment level gain achieved with the microsurgical approach are similar to those obtained with the conventional surgical approach.⁵⁶ A recent meta-analysis found no significant differences in treatment outcomes between minimally invasive periodontal surgery (MIPS) plus biomaterials^{57,58} and MIPS alone, suggesting that costs and benefits should be carefully considered when selecting a regenerative therapeutic modality.^{59,60}

Isolated interproximal defects, typically limited to the interproximal site, are ideal for bone grafting with MIPS. However, generalized horizontal bone loss and multiple interconnected intrabony defects are contraindications for MIPS and are best managed with conventional surgical approaches. In MIPS, a head-mounted operating microscope (Varioscope®) with appropriate lighting is preferable to a surgical microscope as it allows easier visualization of the defect from different angles for proper debridement of the periodontal defect and root surfaces.

In addition to MIPS, minimally invasive nonsurgical therapy has shown significant clinical and radiographic improvements for treating

periodontal intrabony defects.⁶¹

Recently, a new microsurgical approach for periodontal regeneration called the “Entire Papilla Preservation Technique” (EPP) has been described. This technique involves creating an interdental tunnel through the defect-associated papilla with a beveled vertical releasing incision in the buccal gingiva of the adjacent interdental space.⁶² After removing granulation tissue and debriding the root surface, regenerative materials such as bone grafts and enamel matrix derivative are applied. The primary advantage of the EPP technique is enhanced wound stability and limited premature exposure of regenerative biomaterials.

Mucogingival Surgery: Achieving excellent results in terms of esthetics and function requires extremely fine and accurate incisions, meticulous suturing for stabilization and immobilization of the graft, and precise closure of wound margins.⁶³ Thus, the use of a surgical microscope in mucogingival therapy can be beneficial for sites where esthetics demand complete and perfect coverage. Periodontal microsurgery performed by a trained and skilled surgeon offers improved outcomes for root coverage procedures and interdental papilla augmentation.⁷⁰ Compared to the conventional macrosurgical approach for treating gingival recession, the microsurgical approach offers distinct advantages,^{71,72,73} including increased vascularization of grafts, higher percentages of root coverage, a significant increase in the width and thickness of keratinized tissue, improved esthetic outcomes, and decreased patient morbidity.^{74,75}

Implant Therapy: The surgical microscope can be a valuable tool in implant dentistry.⁷⁶ Various stages of implant treatment, from implant placement to recovery and peri-implantitis management, can be performed with greater precision under magnification.⁷⁷ One novel application of microsurgery in implant dentistry is the sinus lift procedure, which has a success rate of 97%.⁷⁸ The surgical microscope aids in the indirect visualization of the sinus membrane and minimizes the risk of perforations.⁷⁹ Microsurgical techniques have also been reported to improve altered sensations due to implants encroaching on the inferior alveolar nerve, even without unscrewing them.⁸⁰

Crown Lengthening and Ridge Augmentation: Although comparative studies of crown lengthening and ridge augmentation using microsurgical methods are limited,⁸¹ it seems logical to conclude that magnification is beneficial for these procedures.^{82,83}

Despite the numerous advantages associated with microsurgical principles and techniques, the limited adoption of microsurgery in periodontal surgical practice may be attributed to several inherent drawbacks. These include constrained visual fields, diminished depth of field and visual reference points, a steep learning curve, and the relatively high initial costs associated with setting up microsurgical equipment.⁸⁴

Recent advancements in microsurgery include innovative technologies such as a three-dimensional on-screen microsurgery system, which provides a three-dimensional view of the surgical field on a video monitor, eliminating the need for direct physical visualization.⁸⁵ Another development is the HDTV single camera 3D system, which integrates a high-definition display with a microscope to enhance visualization. Additionally, the mechanical optical rotating assembly interface allows clinicians to adjust their working positions for improved flexibility during procedures.⁸⁶

Conclusion

Analysis of the data gathered from the reviewed literature supports the notion that periodontal microsurgery demonstrates encouraging clinical outcomes and is increasingly accepted by both clinicians and patients. As the advantages of magnification in periodontal surgical procedures become evident, its integration into global periodontal practices is expected to evolve into a treatment standard in the future.

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